

PECULIARITIES OF ADULTS' PHYSICAL RECREATION THROUGH WUSHU MARTIAL ARTS

Darius-Liviu POPESCU, Angela POLEVAIA-SECĂREANU, Ecaterina LUNGU

State University of Physical Education and Sport (Republic of Moldova)

Corresponding author: dariuspopescu11@gmail.com

Abstract

In this research, the characteristics of physical recreation as a type of physical culture were described and also its main characteristics were highlighted. WUSHU martial arts is considered to be one of the possible ways to organize the physical recreation of adults, presenting its differences and specificity.

Following the analysis of the literature, we found that many authors argue that the socio-medical process of recreating the human being through various means has an important contribution in terms of mental and physical, intellectual, aesthetic, moral, but also the formation of consciousness with on the development of one's personality, character and self-esteem. Regarding the medical aspect, it also addresses the improvement and/or maintenance of the general state of health, the increase of muscular strength, and flexibility, as well as a better quality of life and why not longevity. Thus, the recreation process induces a fairly high value as a degree of social importance, socialization being the psychological process of assimilation, the transmission of concepts and patterns of behaviour specific to a group or community, for training, integration and social adaptation of that person.

Keywords: physical education, physical recreation, adult socializing, martial arts, Wushu

Introduction

As part of physical culture, there are usually a number of components: sports, physical education, rehabilitation, stabilization and physical recreation. It is undeniable that competently selected physical activity is necessary for a person of any age. All activities aimed at preventing premature aging, the formation of a healthy lifestyle include means of physical education. Sports tasks and participation in competitions may not be available to every adult due to employment, health and other reasons, and physical recreation, i.e., physical exercise for the sake of rest and pleasure, may be an excellent basis for maintaining a healthy lifestyle and establishing social contacts.

The term "recreation" in Latin means restoration. Thus, V.P. Zaitsev [6] gives the following definition: "Physical recreation is an active and passive recreation in combination with recreational activities other than production, scientific, educational and other activities aimed at training, restoring, strengthening and preserving human health, as well as bringing pleasure and satisfaction from them, but using the means of physical culture and its forms and methods of formation". Among the main signs of recreation, we highlight the following:

- It is based on motor activity, and exercise is used as the main means, which significantly distinguishes recreation from other hobbies (music, crocheting, etc.).

- It contains intellectual and emotional components, i.e., a person in the process of involvement in physical recreation not only improves physical qualities but also receives the possibility of harmonious development in the process of knowing the world. In this context, the important role of both intelligence and bodily experience in cognitive activity is worth emphasizing.

- He is creative, he has a playful character. Play in physical culture is different (sports games, play as an element of children's physical education, play in martial arts, etc.). In the classic work "Homo Ludens" by Johan Huizinga, given the universal significance of the game

in human civilization, he draws attention to the game in the field of sports, highlighting a number of features. He notes in particular the transition from occasional competitions to competitions with regular motives and strict organizing laws. As Huizinga observes, "Now, with more and more systematization and more rigorous discipline of the game, some of its pure game content is completely lost. The behavior of a professional is no longer a game behavior, spontaneity and indifference do not I'm still in it" [3].

- Includes cultural and value issues. Most types of physical recreation for adults involve not only performing certain exercises but also developing elements of the culture of other countries (national martial arts, oriental practices, etc.).

The activities are carried out in their free time from work or study and bring pleasure to the practitioners. A person independently chooses for himself the time and place of activities and correctly distributes his work and rest.

Examples of physical recreation activities can be courses in oriental health systems, tourism, swimming, visiting fitness clubs, martial arts, sports dancing, etc. Most of these activities as a hobby, from our point of view, can contribute to increasing the indicators of physical performance and the value of health, and to reducing the level of situational anxiety, increasing the level of sociability, increasing the level of social creativity of the individual. Such features allow people of different ages, professions, and interests to engage in physical recreation, which will allow you to seriously expand the circle of communication.

The multiplicity of recreational processes implemented in the daily activities of citizens, innovative methods and actions, highlights not only the value of harmonious physical development and beneficial effects on health but also moral, aesthetic, intellectual and volitional values that accompany motor skills and abilities, all these contributing to a unique formation of the consciousness of the citizen's behavior in the society.

Thus, we can say that the recreation process as an integral part of general education, can contribute in an optimal way through its specific content to the fulfillment of the social ideal as well as in the direction of health, as are the objectives of W.H.O. (World Health Organization) - by forming and creating a multicultural, healthy and long-lived personality.

Here, based on the social ideal through the process of recreation in everyday life, it can be established, in our opinion, that the role of the recreational process is an educational-social-sports ideal with great benefits and general health. If the ideal, in general, would include the implementation of the means of Wushu (martial arts) in the recreational phenomenon, then it could refer to two extremely interesting aspects:

- the formation of modern society through the implementation of Wushu means, this being a traditional-modern style widely used internationally;
- benefits on general health, maintenance and/or improvement, well-being and life expectancy - longevity.

The idea of outlining a model of the individual who regularly participates in the recreation process, whose main major features must reflect the understanding of the importance of his involvement in such recreational processes, is to maintain and/or improve optimal health and focus constantly on this, to get to know the value of a personal physical condition in terms of the balance between the exercise-training technique applied and natural nutrition corroborated with a proper lifestyle.

An interesting feature of this model is that this recreational process also acts intellectually, morally, volitionally, which also brings a civic feeling, with the development of the spirit of honesty and sincerity (fair play) and the ability to develop relationships with the people around you, becoming more sociable and friendly.

Last but not least, the model of the person participating in such recreational activities must be aware of its value and benefits and continue to practice and aspire to these indisputable values throughout life regardless of age, material or financial condition.

Thus, the **purpose of the research** is to introduce the means of Wushu - martial arts, in the phenomenon of recreation of adults and not only, in order to have beneficial effects on health, longevity and well-being.

Methodology

As **research methods** were the analysis and generalization of the literature, observation and comparative method.

Results and Discussion

Recreation stimulates the development of creative freedom, and self-realization, and promotes self-education. Researcher S.N. Rekhovskaya considered the motives of adults who encourage them to engage in physical recreation [4]. Thus, in all groups of subjects, first and foremost in terms of prevalence is such a reason for engaging in physical recreation as self-improvement, and the last places in terms of importance are occupied by the reasons for obtaining the result. Which is perfectly natural, because getting the highest results is not the goal of physical recreation.

But the desire for self-improvement and harmonious development of the physical, spiritual, social aspects of the personality is the most important factor in the use of the means of physical recreation in human life. But despite the variety of options available for physical recreation, there is still a high level of illness and health disorders associated with physical inactivity in society. For adults, we recommend paying attention to non-cyclical, playful activities, in which the formation of a social circle takes place, as well as only those types of activities that provoke positive emotions.

As a living example of a modern type of physical recreation, we can mention the style of martial arts Wushu. Also known as Wushu Kung Fu, it is the collective term for all martial arts from China and developed over thousands of years. There are many systems and styles in Wushu, each incorporating its own techniques, tactics, principles and methods, as well as many traditional weapons. Wushu is not just about fighting or martial arts, but also about improving one's health or philosophy. Nowadays, Wushu has developed as a global sport, practiced and enjoyed by athletes around the world, precisely because of its unique and attractive content.

Wushu and its variants are suitable for anyone who wants to recreate and get at the same time an excellent physical shape, but also to learn very effective (or practical) self-defense techniques. A specific feature is that Wushu practitioners develop the ability or ability to defend themselves both at close range and at long range in real combat situations.

The training aims to learn effective fighting techniques, motivating practitioners to effectively develop different skills, self-confidence and the development of a strong body and a strong mind.

After the proclamation of the People's Republic of China on October 1, 1949, Wushu became a basic component of physical culture and sports, experiencing spectacular development under the guidance and support of the government. The state commission set up a Wushu Institute in Beijing, which is the largest center for the study of theory, exchange of experience, and tended to become an international Wushu academy with the following profile structure:

Fig. 1. Structure of the martial arts Wushu

The collective image of the Wushu style technique has its own characteristics and requires different physical, tactical, technical and mental predispositions of the practitioner. The Wushu technique contains many tricks and imposes great demands on the coordination of the athlete's movements. It is designed in such a way that, with a minimum trajectory and a high speed of execution, the blows offer a strong attack and a reliable defense, and the alternation of relaxation and muscle tension with constant movement increases the fighter's resistance and hinders the opponent's attack.

A feature of Wushu is a large number of strokes, which require a perfect sense of balance. When an athlete performs a kick, additional effort is required to maintain balance on one leg. The development of coordination is extremely necessary in the acrobatic elements as well, so in Wushu, for example, there are about 10 types of jump shots. Endurance as a physical quality is necessary to maintain a high pace of combat during matches and to ensure a long training process. Speed-power skills are required when performing unexpected blows to the opponent. An athlete with a high level of speed skills has an advantage in performing offensive and defensive actions. Flexibility is important for mastering a wide arsenal of strokes, performing acrobatics ("teng kong fei jiao", "xuan feng jiao"). Even elements such as dodging and "split kick" in Wushu serve as an escape from the blow, as well as indicators of the culture of the specific Wushu movement, diversifying its fighting technique.

From the point of view of intellectual improvement, Wushu as a type of physical recreation develops the ability to learn foreign languages (for example, all movements, names are in Chinese, and many masters speak English at seminars and/or competitions), helps to master the elements of the culture of other countries and peoples and promotes the learning of new cultural habits. In addition, modern neuroscience research shows that attending seminars [5] and learning martial arts techniques and elements, become new motor skills [1] or memorize a large amount of information [2] affect brain structures and have a positive effect on intellectual development.

From another point of view, the activity of recreation through the application of Wushu means, can offer, not as a main plan, two other basic categories through the very structure and dynamism that Wushu means includes:

a) Participation in sporting events, competitions, tournaments, Olympics - these include a wide range of disciplines, which are organized in clubs or educational institutions to which it is addressed. Specific preparation for such events will involve transcending the form of the recreation process into a more serious training process, requiring longer-term involvement, motivation and dedication from the practical side;

b) The accumulation of technical knowledge and the possibility of practicing to reach a level of mastery that will make him an expert in the field of martial arts. He can thus become a performance athlete, an instructor or a coach, he can engage in the police or military system, or as bodyguard, etc.

The way in which recreational activities, whether through Wushu, can influence positive employees, for example, can be listed as follows:

- Teamwork, coordination and cooperation;
- One of the major benefits of taking care of the business can be beneficial for the individual and for example the organization as a whole where he works, is that they help in the purpose of teamwork, coordination and cooperation between employees;
- Improves interaction;
- Reduces stress;
- The stress of demanding job requirements, if not well managed, can be a great variety for one's energy and productivity. Not to mention the adverse health impact associated with high levels of stress. Therefore, introducing fun through recreational activities at work could go a long way in reducing stress among employees, thus creating performance at work;
- Promotes creativity and motivation;
- The introduction of fun elements and recreational activities, here and there, in the daily work routine, is also required to give an employee the much needed break, which could be instrumental in stimulating creativity and encouraging outside ideas;
- Makes the atmosphere in the work environment more fun.

Conclusions

Nowadays, an adult has health problems, often associated with a low level of motor activity (hypokinesia, physical inactivity). The concept of health includes not only the absence of disease but also the complete state of physical, mental, spiritual and social well-being of a person. In this state of affairs, physical recreation, as an element of physical education for adults, becomes an important factor for the harmonious development of the individual due to his concentration on communication, the formation of a good mood in physical activity and the promotion of health.

The process of recreation by applying the means of Wushu, in our opinion and the specialists from the field of education-recreation-socio-sports, can effectively represent the system of the fulfillment of the aspects and objectives integrated into the W.H.O. on health benefits. Thus, the recreation process applied to the segment of the adult population acquires a value of the utmost importance, because the practitioner is in an evolutionary, social process with impressive values on the benefits it brings, social benefits, health, openness new horizons, physical and mental relaxation, sharpening of personal skills, socialization, psychological "well-being" and last but not least the possibility of acquiring valuable self-defense techniques to help him in the possibility of an attack on his physical integrity.

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